

**IT IS THE MAIN GUARANTEE OF CONSUMER RIGHTS PROTECTION
TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE CHARACTERISTICS OF
INTERNATIONAL STANDARD REQUIREMENTS.**

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Annotation: The article describes quality and product quality. The effectiveness of measures to improve the quality of their products was discussed. The article argues that improving the quality of agricultural products will serve to fully meet the needs of the population in food, increase the efficiency of agricultural production.

Key words: Own standard, test, calibrate, label, export, Own DST, modification.

The consumer is always right, but if a citizen buys any product from a store or market, he does not pay much attention to its quality [1]. This point may lead to the purchase of a poor quality item or product. Therefore, first of all, every buyer and consumer should pay attention to the suitability of the quality of the purchased product.

In our country, the Uzstandart agency and its local departments are responsible for monitoring the quality and suitability of manufactured products [2]. In this regard, the team of the state unitary enterprise of the Scientific Testing and Quality Control Center of Uzbekistan is doing a number of positive things [3].

- We organize our activities in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Protection of Consumer Rights", the decision of the Cabinet of

Ministers "On measures to simplify the promotion of product certification", says the company. Director [4]. - We can happily say that the introduction of new technologies into the certification process makes our work much easier [5]. The establishment of certification offices for food, agriculture, light industry, construction, mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, oil and chemical products indicates that the scope of the system is expanding [6]. Due to the fact that every product needs to be certified, necessary conditions have been created for customers who come to certify their products. The center is the regional branch of the Federation of Consumer Protection Societies, the Chamber of Commerce and Industry, and works hard to prevent the entry of low-quality, unfit for consumption products into nature. Also, in order to prevent such situations, public control was launched [7].

During 9 months of last year, the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Certification of Products and Services" "On Quality and Safety of Food Products" "On Protection of Consumer Rights" 1741 certificates of compliance were issued by the center's certification offices from law students. In addition, 572 certificates of conformity will be issued as a result of selection (selection) of the certificate of conformity of the Commonwealth of Nations countries. Products worth 38,673 soums were found to be unfit, and a certificate of conformity was refused [8] .

- A testing laboratory for food and agricultural products will soon start operating in Beruni district. If this laboratory starts working, a number of conveniences will be created for entrepreneurs in the future [9].

- Compliance of the products with the requirements of the international standard "ISO-9001" first of all opens the way to the foreign market, - said F. Shukurov, a specialist of the company's quality systems implementation department in an interview with us. enough. Such products are also taken to exhibitions. These products do not reach consumers. As a result, doubts arise about the quality of the manufactured product [10].

And the "ISO - 9001" quality management system certificate prevents this. It guarantees 100 percent product quality [11]. Therefore, there are many buyers of products with this certificate all over the world. We are focusing on this process. Currently, the center is working on a special department for the implementation of the quality system. Implementation of quality management systems in accordance with the requirements of the international standard "ISO-9001" is underway [12]. National Metrology Institute of the Republic of Uzbekistan State Enterprise Jizzakh Branch, "Uzbekistan Scientific Testing and Quality Control Center State Unitary Enterprise [13], Jizzakh Regional Power Network Enterprise JSC, Jizzakh Regional State Sanitary and Epidemiological Center, Agro-Industrial Complex Service Center DUK Jizzakh including branch offices [14].

Promotional work is important for the development of any industry. With this in mind, Sokha experts are holding a meeting and seminar [15].

Three accredited laboratories are working in the center. These are testing laboratories for low-voltage electrical products, motor vehicles, and physical and chemical parameters [16]. The equipment in them was repaired and new equipment was brought. As a result, the accreditation activity of the enterprise improved. In particular, it was possible to more closely check the quality of fish products and gusht, to determine the color of Usmilik oil [17].

In short, the team of the state unitary enterprise of the Scientific Testing and Quality Control Center of Uzbekistan is making a worthy contribution to providing the domestic market of our republic with quality products and protecting the rights of consumers [18].

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